

Reliability of data-based applications in society and decision-making

Interview with Caroline Jay

July 29, 2024, 10:04AM

Caroline Jay is a Professor of Computer Science and Head of Research in the School of Engineering at the University of Manchester. She is also a Chartered Psychologist and a Fellow of the Alan Turing Institute, using an understanding of human behaviour to improve the way we design Artificial Intelligence. Caroline is the Research Director of the Software Sustainability Institute, and a keen advocate for open and reproducible science.

Khan, Hamid started transcription

Khan, Hamid 0:05

[Following introductions] Can you talk to us about what the term Artificial Intelligence means and how Artificial Intelligence is used in decision-making or to support decision-making in general?

Caroline Jay 4:00

As a computer scientist, I find the term Artificial Intelligence not terribly meaningful. I still use it because within the public domain people have some idea of what that might mean.

Of course, it's a collection of different technologies, and it's never really what we tend to mean when we talk about it in the public domain: things like machine learning, particularly from the perspective of neural networks, black-box machine learning. But it can be potentially lots of other things, as well. We have symbolic AI, which is rule-based, which is something that we've had for many, many years, predating things like neural networks.

So, my perspective on AI is it's not a meaningful term, because it's a collection of technologies that ideally help with things like prediction and classification.

In terms of decision-making, I do some work within healthcare, and I'm interested in understanding how we can develop explainable AI techniques. In particular, at the

moment, I have a project looking at ECG [electrocardiogram] interpretation. What we're doing is using visualisation techniques to change how we present ECG data, so that members of the public find it easier to understand, and, as part of this, we also develop automated algorithms. But we're doing that in parallel, so we're hopefully creating more explainable forms of AI because we know that people and machines are sharing the same representation of the data. That's my personal interest in it from a clinical perspective.

We work with clinicians to understand what they want from this. That's a whole other discussion, so we won't get too far into that. But in terms of decision-making more generally, we want to be able to understand the provenance of any information that we are using for making decisions.

My personal perspective is that we should use tools to help us, and machine learning, from the perspective of its ability to make predictions, can help with that. But obviously it becomes challenging when we're using these tools in a naive way and accepting whatever they're saying when we don't really know where that information comes from.

Khan, Hamid 6:35

As you've identified, there is a lack of common language around some of these concepts, and particularly when we do things like public involvement and public engagement that can pose a challenge in itself, in terms of people starting from different points.

We often talk about concepts like explainability and reliability and validity. From your perspective and your experience, what do you think the term reliability means in the context of decision-making tools like AI?

Caroline Jay 7:24

Again, all of these terms have slightly different meanings depending on the context. What we're looking for in terms of reliability is some consistency in the results. Given a particular input, we'd expect either the same or a very similar output over time, so it's that consistency over time.

Khan, Hamid 7:54

And, if we think about the ways that models and AI are used in decision-making, for example in healthcare and patient treatment, what do you see as the biggest challenges to reliability in general?

Caroline Jay 8:12

The data that models are trained [on]. To clarify, I'll talk primarily about statistical machine learning, because I think that's the technology that's being used most. Of course, how these things work depends on the underlying algorithms we're using.

The data that we're training models on is important. I was, just before we started talking, reading an interesting paper in Nature showing how, if you train models on data generated by AI, you quickly get model collapse and it all goes wrong, which is very interesting and also extremely reassuring because it shows that the human in the loop is really important here anyway.

In terms of reliability, the main concern is the data that models trained on, and I think that is probably the key thing. It's that input very early on, and if we don't have appropriate training data to support our overall goal, then we're going to get into major issues.

Just to get into where some of the real issues lie, I have discussions with colleagues around things like populations that data is drawn from, characteristics of people in those populations and how we manage that.

An example of a really challenging problem is if we have data [from] men, when we are trying to apply those models to women, it might not work. That's [a] fairly basic example. And we do that a lot within healthcare, not just with an AI, it's a big problem. We test drugs on men and not women.

It's really challenging in a lot of other areas, as well. One of the things we talk about is underrepresented groups. This came up over Covid quite a lot in terms of people being differentially affected by Covid and then people trying to hypothesise as to why that was. Ethnicity was brought into the mix and that's extremely difficult to define.

There are ways of classifying people's ethnicity, but it's very hard to do it effectively. We ended up with that being used inappropriately. In fact, we can see that it's not necessarily ethnicity that is the issue, but rather people's circumstances and where they're living and so on.

These [are] really challenging problems to understand and explain. And I think we don't really know at the moment how to manage these kinds of situations and what kinds of factors we should consider.

Khan, Hamid 11:16

Now that you mentioned Covid, are there other case studies where AI has been used quite well, perhaps in management of Covid or outside of that in your field, as well?

Caroline Jay 11:30

Well, depends on what you mean by AI. Obviously, mathematical modelling has been used in really useful ways, but that's not really AI.

I know there's some work done with the Zoe app¹.

I know they're looking at population spread, but I'm not sure that I can really answer that question because I'd need to look back at the papers to distinguish between what was just a statistical model and what was AI, so I'll probably leave that.

Khan, Hamid 12:25

That brings up interesting side points about what really is the difference between a model and an AI? Is there something that is a real AI in the sci-fi depiction of it compared to just an advanced machine learning model. Is that a conflation that people make?

Caroline Jay 12:52

Yes, I think the term AI means lots of different things. People tend to think of things like ChatGPT now when they think about AI, or maybe robots, something that can talk to them. They view it as intelligent in the way that they might view a person.

¹ See [ZOE—Understand how food affects your body](#) [accessed 11-09-2024].

I think we're moving more towards that, but it's a term that's used everywhere. It's kind of ubiquitous, and there's no proper definition given to it most of the time.

Khan, Hamid 13:26

Conversely, are there examples that come to mind where a model or AI in decision-making has been used in an unreliable way or in a way that has caused unpredicted harm?

Caroline Jay 13:45

I know that over the years there have been lots of examples of this from facial recognition technology not working very well and lots of high-profile news stories about that. I think that's one of the main ones, and that actively causes harm because it has resulted in innocent people being arrested when they shouldn't have been, because the model hasn't been trained on appropriate data. That's probably one of the key ones.

There probably are instances where these harms are being caused, but we're perhaps not aware of it at the moment. And I think, again, this happens outside of AI. I think this happens everywhere all the time when it comes to decision-making. We're not aware of the full picture or the biases that might be at play when we're making decisions.

Khan, Hamid 14:54

A lot of these applications, if they go wrong, can have quite serious consequences for public life. As you say, people being arrested for the wrong reasons, and particularly in patient treatment there's a risk of unpredicted harms. Is there a role then for the public in terms of developing an approach to scrutinising data, models and AI in decision-making before it gets to the stage where it affects them?

Caroline Jay 15:30

Yes, absolutely. One of the things that I am really keen on, and I'm trying to do within my own projects, is speak with people before the point where you start getting into developing the technology, so that you can understand their perspectives.

There's a piece of work that we did recently, which we haven't published yet, but we were looking at developing framework for responsible research and innovation.

Patient involvement is reasonably well established now in within healthcare research. Certainly within healthcare technology research, there's an expectation when a proposal is funded, that patients will be involved in development, or stakeholders, more widely. But I think this idea of including the public voice more is really important as well, because when you're in the technology bubble, it is quite easy to only see the technology.

Perhaps we're getting a bit better, but generally speaking, somebody who's involved in developing technology tends to think about what the technology can do and is very focussed on that and much less focussed on all the other stuff – for example, what the implications of it might be, whether people actually want it, whether it's working in a way that people find acceptable, and whether it has potential that hasn't been recognised yet. This idea of involving the public earlier on in the discussion around these technologies is really important. And that doesn't happen very much at the moment, for a couple of reasons.

The first one is that [technology developers, including researchers] don't necessarily see the value, and I think that's because often the value is coming to understand something that you didn't know already, hopefully. Because that's in these discussions, and obviously it's quite difficult in advance to know what that might be. It's perceived that you're not going to be told anything that you don't already know.

The other thing is, and this comes back to open research practices, it's very resource-intensive. Trying to talk with [the public] about things and then analyse that data is extremely resource intensive, even just getting people together and scheduling a time to meet. [Researchers] find it hard to justify taking that time. I do wonder whether we can partly rethink expectations, but also think about how we fund this and how we prioritise it. I don't know quite what the model looks like, but I think it would be great to do more of it.

Khan, Hamid 18:43

You mentioned that you have started to embed early public engagement into your own research and practices. Is that something that is happening at an institutional level or something you've taken the initiative to do?

Caroline Jay 18:57

Within the University of Manchester, we have been doing this for a while. The SYNBIOCHEM project² has a stream of work looking specifically at this. We're trying to do it as part of the ECG-X project³, and we are looking at an institutional level at how we can support this better. We haven't fully adopted it at an institutional level yet, but we are trying to work out how we could do that. For example, we have some resources on our website that help support researchers in doing this. There's still quite a long way to go, but we are moving in that direction.

Khan, Hamid 19:38

Patient involvement is quite well established. But you were saying that's maybe one group of "publics", and there are other publics that could be involved, as well. If you were developing, for example, a decision-making tool in healthcare, based on a model or an AI, who would you see as the key stakeholders that would need to be involved in a consultation or engagement process around that?

Caroline Jay 20:13

In terms of stakeholders, we obviously have patients who would be affected by the decisions, also anyone in a caring position (people close to those patients) and clinicians. I'd say a wide range of clinicians. There are many people who would be involved in the care of the patients, and I think speaking with a range of people would be important. Beyond that, also speaking with just people in general. It depends on the technology, of course.

Particularly when we're thinking about diagnostics and this kind of thing – it might be a mobile app for supporting health in some way – a lot of people [who] would be using that won't currently have a particular condition, but it might help alert them to the fact that they are developing one, for example. So, speaking just with people to understand their perspective is a really helpful thing, as well. That kind of engagement should be as broad as possible.

² See [SYNBIOCHEM | Manchester Synthetic Biology Research Centre for Fine and Speciality Chemicals](#) [accessed: 09-09-2024].

³ See [Clinicians' attitudes to AI – presentation at ICE 2024 – ECG-X](#) [accessed: 28-11-2024]

Khan, Hamid 21:40

It makes us reflect on some of the work going on at Imperial. Very similarly, the patient involvement side is well-developed, and the challenge is to take it to the next level in terms of making sure that the widest possible group of stakeholders are involved.

Focussing on some of the public involvement that we did, what we found was that public participants had a reasonably good understanding of things like the risk of bias in training data and maybe not so much beyond that. Has that been your experience? And, if that's the case, does that pose a problem in terms of truly tackling the question of reliability, if there is this relentless focus on the training data?

Caroline Jay 22:34

The answer to that is, we need to make sure that we are explaining the concepts to people properly. There's a responsibility for the researcher to point out some of the issues that they think might arise and explain how the technology works. Once people have a better understanding of how it works, then they would be in a better position to identify where issues might occur.

Training data comes up a lot within the public domain. That's now captured the public imagination. It's great that people are starting to take that on board, but I think we have to explain how things work in order for people to be able to make informed comments.

Khan, Hamid 23:45

Possibly one way to go is around facilitated workshops, where there is an introduction taking place to some of the concepts followed by the discussion.

We identified some of the challenges. At a practical level, what do we do about it? How do we address the challenges of reliability?

Caroline Jay 24:14

We have to remain alert to these issues. I'm a big fan of empirical research. I think empirical research in this area is really important. This article [["AI models fed AI-generated data quickly spew nonsense"](#), by Elizabeth Gibney, *Nature*, 24-07-2024] is

a great example of empirical work demonstrating some of the problems that we have with AI⁴. This is showing that if you train an AI on AI-generated data, it deteriorates really quickly.

I'm interested in using LLMs [Large Language Models] for programming. Anecdotally, it started to come out that there were issues with this, but actually it's only when we have systematic studies that we can start to see where things break down. That's the thing that's really valuable in understanding where the problems are with the technology.

Khan, Hamid 26:01

Do you think it will ever be possible to develop a generalisable workflow that any researcher or end-user of the technology can adopt as a way of asking the right questions about the source and the nature of the data, about the assumptions the model is making, about the extent to which it can bear the weight that we put on it? Can that ever be an ideal that we realise, or will it always vary from case to case?

Caroline Jay 26:36

I'm generally quite optimistic. I think we can work towards that. The caveat would be that we already don't understand the software that we have.

The reason I'm optimistic that something like this might be possible is that we're already in a situation where we write code that we don't understand. We know that because it's got bugs in, and we didn't [deliberately] write it with the bugs in, did we? We didn't expect to find them there, so we've written something that we don't understand and that's my starting point.

Moving on from that, things like LLMs will be very useful for helping us, for example, to query software systems. I'm doing some work in this area, which is very early stage at the moment, so I haven't got the answers yet, but lots of people are working on this. Can we develop foundation models for something known like a software system? So we use transfer learning to fit it to whatever we're looking at.

⁴ See [AI models fed AI-generated data quickly spew nonsense \(nature.com\)](#) [accessed: 09-09-2024].

Once we've done that, can we use it to interact with that system, to understand it in a way that we didn't do previously? I think that these technologies will help us with understanding complex systems. So, that's good.

There is always a worry, particularly with scientific research, around researchers using techniques they don't fully understand and then coming up with results that are misrepresented within the [journal article]. We know that this is a major issue just using [statistics]. People use stats inappropriately all the time. So, we already know that we have a problem with this; it's not something specific to Artificial Intelligence.

Over time, we will work out how to use these technologies appropriately. I think they can perhaps support understanding as well as introducing complexity, which then reduces understanding, but I do feel reasonably optimistic that we will get a handle on how to use them appropriately, eventually.

Khan, Hamid 28:58

The question ultimately is, if we were able to open up the black box of AI, would we recognise what we saw in there as relatable to the thing that we created in the first place? One of the challenges may be, if it's a true AI, that we won't recognise what's in that black box.

Caroline Jay 29:29

And this is the problem with the term AI, isn't it? We have to understand the tools that we're using, and where we don't fully understand them, we have to find ways of interrogating them and evaluating them empirically, so we can improve our understanding of what's going on.

It is very easy to anthropomorphise. I find myself doing this all the time, thinking: "We've got the machine and the human sharing this representation of the data. That means the machine's interpreting it in the same way as human is." And of course, that's just not true, right? I haven't got any evidence that that's the case. I've got some evidence that it might be the case, but I can't confirm it. It's about viewing it as a tool and trying not to view it as an intelligent being.

Khan, Hamid 30:25

Do we need to start by focussing on things like openness and transparency? Making sure that we are open about data, software and code as the default – is that a good starting point?

Caroline Jay 30:41

Yes. I have been practising Open Research myself for quite a long time, and I think that that's really helpful. Just because something is open, it doesn't necessarily solve the whole problem. There are lots of difficulties from a practical perspective about making things truly open. However, [when] somebody else can look at that code or look at the data you've been using, if they wish to, I think that's extremely helpful.

Khan, Hamid 31:14

What are some of the caveats in your experience? Because you would be using a lot of patient data or working adjacently to patient data. Can we ever have a situation where patient data is open in a meaningful way so that the applications built from that data can be scrutinised?

Caroline Jay 31:39

This is an interesting question. The issue is identifiability. We don't want to be able to identify individuals from any data that we release.

We already do have open datasets. I use some of them for my own research. I will use ECG recordings that are publicly available; there are databases where they're accessible. But from those, it's very difficult to identify individuals, because you don't have a lot of other information about them.

One thing that's really interesting about this [is] that it's very nuanced. I remember a scandal a while ago with regards to medical data. Patients had given their data to a study, or they'd taken part in a study, and they were expecting that this would be shared widely between researchers, so that other people could use that data for their own research. And that wasn't happening, and they were angry about this. There's this idea that we must keep everything confidential and we must keep everything locked down, [but] in fact, a lot of people say: "No, please do use my data. If it means that we'll improve health outcomes, then I'm fine with that."

One always needs to protect an individual, but at the same time, I think probably people would be more open to it than is currently assumed. A lot of the protection is around, understandably again, protecting institutions and protecting researchers from making mistakes, or from inadvertently revealing something that they shouldn't, rather than what's actually in the best interests of patients and the population.

Khan, Hamid 33:54

I hadn't come across that case study before, and it is interesting that there might not necessarily be as strong of a trade-off between privacy and quality as we sometimes assume.

Thinking on that theme of openness and transparency, one of the things that came up in our workshops, mostly when we were talking to researchers and staff, was the need for recognising and incentivising the time and effort that goes into making data and code and software open, preparing it in a meaningful way, and ensuring that the robustness is there when you share it, as well. In your experience, what are some of the things we could do to make sure that openness and transparency are appropriately rewarded?

Caroline Jay 34:59

This is a really tricky one. It has to do with funding. My perspective is this is the biggest obstacle at the moment to Open Research. I think a few things are going to help. The obvious answer is for me to say funding agenc[ies] should fund it properly.

We had a project recently where we [published the final dataset] in Nature Scientific Data, and we put it on Zenodo before that. This is data from other data sources; it's Defra [the Department for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs] data, Met Office data and some of our own data where we made some estimations. It wasn't simulated data, it's interpolated data, where there are missing values. We republished these datasets, because it's extremely difficult to get hold of this data. All of this data is open. However, it's a massive pain to get your hands on it. It took us about 18 months of personal effort to curate this data properly. That's how time-consuming these things are: making sure that the metadata was really good and that all of the data matched, because it's all over different time scales – Met Office will be over one

time scale, Defra data would be over another, and then you'd have to have the estimations, and then you'd want to [know] what region are we talking about? If you want to map it to a spatial region, how do you do that? That's why it took so long. It sounds easy and it's not. It's really difficult doing these things. It took us 18 months.

We published it [along with] a data descriptor paper. The reason we did this is because it had taken us so long. Even publishing the paper was another few months. But we're really glad we did it because the data has had sufficient downloads in the time since then. If each person who downloaded it had had to go through that process themselves, we would have seen it take about 1000 years' worth of person effort. So, it's great that we did that because we know that other people have benefitted from it.

That's all good and so forth, and we can make this case that we should fund this properly. It was the [Alan] Turing Institute that funded this particular project. But let's say UKRI, all they need to do is fund an extra 18 months on each project to do this, and then it'll all be wonderful. But that's just not going to happen because that would cost billions or close to that. Let's say all of the research in the UK for every project, add something on, it would cost a lot of money. That simplistic answer is not really going to work because we just don't have the funds. And particularly at the moment, in the current economic climate, it's going to be very difficult to make that case.

I think what will happen is, first of all, people are just being incentivised more to work in this way. Part of it has to do with that being the expectation of, for example, journals and funders, and part of it has to do with people recognising the benefits. If you publish your data, your paper is more likely to be cited. There are those benefits.

Also, we're developing tools and practices and techniques that are helping to support this. We talk a lot about things like data standards and so on. Of course, the standards are extremely difficult to develop, but over time, as we become used to doing this, we will just get better at doing this.

The postgraduate researchers who I work with, people doing their PhDs, they do this right from the start. Most of them are working with relatively small datasets. But they

just make their code and data open from the start, and it hasn't really been that much of an overhead for them. It probably will have been a bit, but nothing like getting to the end of your study and then suddenly going: "Oh, somebody's told me now that I've got to be [open]. Well, my codes is a mess. What am I going to do about that? And then if I start changing my code, then I've got to test it to make sure I still get the same result. And then I've got to do the metadata". That's going to take time. So, if you just are open from the start and you think about it from the start, then obviously it reduces the overhead.

Generations of researchers coming through are starting to do that a bit more, and then things will start to standardise, and we will have tools that are better able to support us and so on. It's going to be a slow process, but I think that's where we're going to get to hopefully at some point.

Khan, Hamid 40:30

It's interesting you mentioned the postgraduate experience and the fact that they are engaging with more of these things of their own volition. Is that because of the guidance that exists at university level, or is that just because of a certain perception they have that it's their responsibility to do this?

Caroline Jay 40:54

It's a combination of those things. We have an Office for Open Research at the University of Manchester, and we do quite a lot to support Open Research. There is quite a lot of support available for people. Obviously, you have to engage with it to get it. What I'm not going to say is that the whole institution is practising this perfectly because that's not the case, but many researchers are and there is support for those who want to do it.

In the case of the PGRs that I work with, I practise Open Research and my colleagues do, so they have that support there. And also that expectation right from the start, that's what we're going to be doing.

There is absolutely more consciousness around this, and early career researchers are thinking about these things more because they think that is important. In the same way that younger researchers are thinking more from the perspective of principles about the kind of research that they want to do. I think that's probably positive, and I

think the younger generations do tend to think more about things that are going to affect them. Climate change is another good example of this. Separate to research, but they're thinking about it. It's difficult to say for sure, but I think there is just more of an awareness amongst such generation.

Khan, Hamid 42:36

Perhaps it does come down into making sure that some of what they're doing already is being appropriately recognised and making sure that the support systems and the infrastructure are there to encourage them to do more of that.

Caroline Jay 42:47

Yes.

Khan, Hamid 42:55

That brings me neatly on to the next question. Who are the key actors in this? To what extent can an institution like Manchester or Imperial act on this unilaterally? Does it necessarily require action from funders and publishers and governments to make openness and transparency and quality the things that really matter in research?

Caroline Jay 43:21

Institutions absolutely can do things to support people. Some of the initiatives we have at Manchester are [for example] Open Research fellowships. This will buy out somebody's time for usually around a day or half a day a week to focus on Open Research activities. We have a cohort of about six of these going through a year.

We have the Office for Open Research. We have awards each year, an award for Open Research, and we publicise what people are doing. We have case studies. We put them on the website. We send out newsletters, we have a mailing list, where anyone can join and send emails around anyone who's interested in Open Research at the university. That's quite active and has hundreds – I don't know how many exactly, but hundreds – of members.

I definitely think there are things that institutions can do, and it's about creating that culture where you think: "If I'm doing this, I'm going to be rewarded for it."

It's in our promotions criteria, as well. If you're practising Open Research, that's one of the things that would count towards promotions [at] every level. Those things can be done by institutions.

Khan, Hamid 44:31

And if there was just one thing that you would say a university should do in the short to medium term – let's say in the next year or so – that would help to embed this culture of transparency and an expectation of quality and reliability, what do you think that that could be? It's a relatively easy win, shall we say?

Caroline Jay 44:52

I don't know if it's an easy win, but the thing I would say is putting it in the promotions criteria. I think the most important thing here is that people are really short of time and under a lot of pressure. And one of the reasons people don't practise Open Research is because they feel they'll be penalised for it if they do, because they won't be as efficient.

It may not change things straight away, but I think recognising the contributions of those people who do do it by saying this is something that can count towards promotion, and supporting other people in doing it is something that can count towards promotion. I think that would really help, and it's not an immediate financial investment for the university, either. It's a cultural change.

Khan, Hamid 45:38

Do you find that a lot of universities are starting to do that now? Because it's about creating a level playing field and making sure that if one university has a policy of valuing those practices, that their researchers will not be at a disadvantage if they apply for jobs elsewhere.

Caroline Jay 45:51

I don't know. I would hope that universities are doing this, and I'm sure some are, but I don't know how widespread this is.

Khan, Hamid 46:07

One more question: was there anything you were expecting to come up today that didn't and that you'd like to mention?

Caroline Jay 46:20

No, I don't think so. We talked about lots of things that are really interesting and important. So, no, I don't think there's anything specific, nothing burning, that I need to add at this point.

Khan, Hamid 46:39

And hopefully nothing scary or unexpected, either.

I just want to once again thank you, Caroline, for taking the time to do this. And it's not just the fifty-odd minutes here, but it's all the time that goes into thinking and preparing, as well. We're very grateful for it.